

IV bands respectively². The positions of all these bands remain practically unaltered in the present complexes implying non-coordination of thiomido sulphur or nitrogen atoms to metal ions. The band at $\sim 1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to amidic $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ of the ligand is found to be absent and two new bands of medium intensity are observed at ~ 1560 and $\sim 1510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ respectively indicating that the ligand coordinates to the metal ions through deprotonation of enolic OH after enolisation. The band observed at $\sim 1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to azomethine $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ of the ligand is lowered by 10 to 20 cm^{-1} in this complexes implying coordination of azomethine nitrogen to the metal ion. Consequently, the band occurring at 1050 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{N}-\text{N}$ of the ligand is blue shifted to $\sim 1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes suggesting hereby reduction of the repulsion between the lone pair of electrons on N-atoms owing to coordination via azomethine nitrogen atom. In addition to thioamide bands and a band due to azomethine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, a system of bands at ~ 1580 , ~ 1430 , ~ 1000 and $\sim 600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to antisymmetric ring stretching, symmetric ring stretching, ring breathing and in plane deformation mode of pyridine nucleus were observed³.

It became difficult to arrive at any conclusion from the bands occurring at finger print region due to overlapping nature regarding the coordination behavior of ring nitrogen atom of pyridine moiety, however the shifting of band at 600 cm^{-1} to high frequency region by $20\text{--}30\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the present complexes suggests the coordination of pyridine ring nitrogen atom to the metal ion⁴.

The ligand (Htmit) contains both the thiophene ring and thioamide groups. All the bands due to above groups were not observed in the IR spectrum of Htmit. Instead, IR spectrum of this ligand only exhibits bands at ~ 1450 , ~ 1320 , $\sim 1080\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to thioamide I, II and III bands respectively being overlapped with ring stretching vibration of thiophene ring where as the bands observed at ~ 840 and $\sim 810\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned due to thioamide IV band and $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C}$ vibrations respectively². The characteristic IR bands due to $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C}$ (thiophene ring) shifted their positions to lower frequency region there by indicating the coordination of ring sulphur atom to the metal ions⁵. The presence of furan ring in Hfit is also indicated by the appearance of band at 1500 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ group of furan ring². The position of this band is shifted to lower frequency region in the metal complexes suggesting participation of oxygen atom of furan ring in complexation.

In the nitrate complexes of Th^{4+} , two additional bands at ~ 1390 , $\sim 1020\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed. These spectral features provide unequivocal evidence for coordination of nitrate ion in unidentate manner corresponding to ν_2 and ν_4 mode of vibration of coordinated nitrate ion under C_{2v} symmetry⁶. The presence of nitrate ion in the coordination sphere of Th^{IV} has also been supported by non electrolytic nature of complexes in DMSO. The occurrence of new bands at $530\text{--}520$, $460\text{--}450$ and $320\text{--}310\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of complexes further suggest the coordination of metal ions through oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur atom assignable to M-O and M-N and M-S stretching vibration respectively. Uranyl complexes exhibit a strong band at $940\text{--}900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and medium intensity band at $\sim 835\text{--}820\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{as}}\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O}$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O}$ mode respectively⁷. The zirconyl complexes exhibit one strong band in the region $\sim 900\text{--}870\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be attributed to the $\nu\text{Zr}=\text{O}$ as reported earlier indicating the presence of $(\text{Zr}=\text{O})^{2+}$ moiety in these complexes⁸. Besides the above bands, a broad band at $\sim 3600\text{ cm}^{-1}(\text{s})$ is also observed in the complexes which may be predicted to be due to the lattice water as evidenced from the absence of the band due to rocking mode of vibration and thermal analysis.

Thermal analysis :

The complexes formed by the ligands Hpmit, Htmit, Hfit follow the same pattern of thermal decomposition. The complexes remain almost unaffected upto $50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. After this a slight depression upto $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is observed. The weight loss at this temperature range is equivalent to two water molecules for tmit and fit complexes and Hpmit complexes where as one water molecule for other complexes of pmit in conformity with our earlier observation from analytical and IR spectral investigation. The anhydrous complexes remain stable up to $\sim 330\text{--}420\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and thereafter show rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of ligand constituents as indicated by the steep fall in the percentage weight loss. The decomposition continues up to $\sim 600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and reaches a stable product in each complex as indicated by the consistency in weight in the plateau of the thermogram. This corresponds to the composition of their stable oxides such as U_3O_8 , ZrO_2 and ThO_2 . Thermal stabilities of the complexes are found to be in the order :

(pmit) complexes : $\text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}} < \text{ZrO}^{\text{IV}} < \text{Th}^{\text{IV}}$

(tmit) complexes : $\text{Th}^{\text{IV}} < \text{ZrO}^{\text{IV}} < \text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}}$

(fit) complexes : $\text{Th}^{\text{IV}} < \text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}} < \text{ZrO}^{\text{IV}}$

Electronic and ¹H NMR spectra :

All the ligands display only two bands corresponding to λ_{\max} 250–280 and 330–350 nm assignable to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition respectively indicating extensive conjugation.

The spectra of UO_2^{VI} complexes display mainly one weak band at 440 nm and a highly intense band in the range 300–310 nm, which may be due to $^1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow ^3\Pi_u$ transition and charge transfer transition respectively⁹. It may be noted that the band occurring at 370 nm due to uranyl moiety because of apical oxygen $\rightarrow f^0(U)$ transition, which is being merged with the ligand band due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition as evident from broadness and intensity. The electronic spectra of Th^{IV} and ZrO^{IV} complexes exhibit only highly intensive additional band in the region 380–400 nm which may be due to charge transfer besides the ligand bands.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands and complexes are recorded in DMSO-*d*₆-CDCl₃ medium. The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands show a complex broad multiplet at δ 8.5–7.0 ppm corresponding to four aromatic protons for pyridine moiety of Hpmit, at δ 7.78–7.22 corresponding to three protons of thiophene moiety of Htmit and at δ 7.4–6.30 ppm corresponding to three protons of furan moiety of Hfit. The above multiplets due to ring protons undergo downfield shift to some extent probably due to involvement of ring N atom, ring S atom and ring O atom in complexation because of lowering of electron density in the ring system as evidenced from IR investigation.

Three distinct ¹H NMR peaks are observed at $\sim \delta$ 9.5 ppm (1H), $\sim \delta$ 9.1 ppm (1H) and at $\sim \delta$ 3.42 ppm in the present system of ligands corresponding to N=C–H proton, –NH proton and –CH₂ protons (thiohydantoin moiety). The signal due to H–C=N proton shows a downfield shift by δ 0.2–0.4 ppm indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen. The proton signal due to –CH₂ proton of the ligand is shifted to downfield region ($\sim \delta$ 5.82 ppm) corresponding to single proton there by indicating involvement of one hydrogen atom of CH₂ group in enolisation through tautomerism. However, the positions of other bands do not change appreciably because of the coordination of the ligand with metal ions.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used in the present study. The ligands such as Hpmit, Htmit and Hfit were prepared by adopting literature methods¹⁰ by condensing

thiosemicarbazones of pyridine 2-aldehyde, thienyl 2-aldehyde and furfural 2-aldehyde respectively with monochloroacetic acid in dry pyridine. They were recrystallized from ethanol and their purities were checked by melting point, elemental analysis followed by spectral investigations.

Preparation of the complexes of the type $[ML_2].nH_2O$ and $[ThL_2(NO_3)_2].2H_2O$; $M = UO_2^{VI}$ and ZrO^{IV} :

Hot ethanolic solutions of the ligands, HL (0.01 mol) were mixed with corresponding hydrated $UO_2^{VI}/ZrO^{IV}/Th^{IV}$ nitrates (0.005 mol) dissolved in minimum volume of ethanol and the pH of the resulting solutions were adjusted to ~ 6 by dropwise addition of dilute ammonia. UO_2^{VI} complexes separated out immediately, while complexes of ZrO^{IV} and Th^{IV} were obtained only after refluxing for 8–9 h on a hot water bath. In each case, micro crystalline coloured complex was obtained which was filtered, washed several times with ethanol followed by ether and finally dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl₂.

Uranium, zirconium and thorium contents were determined as U₃O₈, ZrO₂ and ThO₂ respectively by standard method¹¹. C, H and N contents were determined by micro analysis using MLW-CHN micro analyzer, where as sulphur content was estimated as BaSO₄.

The molar conductance measurements were carried out at room temperature with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge (Model CL-01-06, cell constant 0.5 cm⁻¹) using 1×10^{-3} M solution of the complexes in DMSO. FTIR spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Varian FTIR spectrophotometer, Australia. The electronic spectra of the complexes in DMSO were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Thermo gravimetric analysis was done by Netzsch-429 thermoanalyser recording at a rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ in air. Around 90–115 mg of the sample was used in each case. The ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆-CDCl₃ medium on JEOL GSX-400 model equipment.

Purities of these complexes were established by TLC on silica gel. The colour and analytical data of the complexes are summarized in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the services rendered by Director, Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Center, IIT, Chennai, for recording the spectra.

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